

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE MECHANICAL AND FLAMMABILITY BEHAVIOUR OF SILICA AND RUBBER NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

The widespread use of epoxy polymers in engineering is due to their outstanding mechanical properties such as high stiffness and high strength combined with low density which results in high performance lightweight structures. However, the highly cross-linked network structure is responsible for the brittle behaviour. The addition of nanoparticles to toughen the polymer can alleviate this undesired brittleness, typically been achieved by the addition of a rubbery phase such as core shell rubber (CSR) particles. In most applications, epoxy resins are required to pass fire resistance safety standards. The demands of increased toughness and improved fire resistance are often antagonistic. Nano-additives such as silica nanoparticles have been shown to promote flame retardant properties even at low additive loading, leading to improvements in thermal properties [1], although leading to a reduction in mechanical properties especially toughness. However, composite systems with simultaneously excellent fire resistance and toughness properties are possible as presented in this work.

2 Experimental Methods

The samples used were cast from Bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA) and hardened using isophorone diamine (Vestamin IPD, Evonik Industries, Germany). 18% reactive diluent of 1,6-hexanediol diglycidylether (HDDGE) was added to lower the viscosity and ease processing. Nano-silica with an average diameter of 20 nm (pre-dispersed at 40% in DGEBA, Nanopox F400, Evonik Hanse, Germany) was added at 3 concentrations of 12 wt.%, 24wt.% and 30.5wt.%. The same concentrations were achieved with CSR nanoparticles (Albidur, EP2240A, Evonik Hanse, Germany). The stoichiometric ratios of resin to curing

agent were adjusted accordingly. Single-iedge notched bending (SENB) tests were performed to obtain the fracture energy, G_{IC} . The flammability tests were performed using standard cone heater, illustrated in Figure 1. Samples machined into 90×90 mm² plaques of 10 mm thickness were exposed to 30 kW/m² up to the point of spontaneous ignition. The heat flux was calibrated before each test using a Huskeflux SBG01 heat flux gauge and the core temperature of the sample was monitored via a K-type thermocouple embedded into the sample at a depth of 5 mm. After ignition, the sample was immediately extinguished in cold water bath of 10 mm depth and fixed by encasing it in a low viscosity epoxy resin for microscopic investigation, to preserve and study the fragile skin.

3 Results and discussion

The fracture properties of samples modified with silica nanoparticles are given in Figure 2. It can be seen that the addition of solely silica nanoparticles results in an increase in fracture toughness up to 24 wt.% with a reduction in toughness noted at higher particle loadings. Figure 3 presents the measured fracture energies with increasing addition of CSR particles. The latter are much more effective at toughening the resin than the silica nanoparticles in Figure 2 with a maximum fracture toughness of 5.44kJ/m² measured for an epoxy system containing 24 wt.% of CSR particles. It can be seen from Figures 2 and 3 that by designing a hybrid composite such that it contains a small amount of CSR particles and is subsequently heavily filled with silica nanoparticles, only a small loss in measured fracture energy is noted over the samples modified with solely CSR nanoparticles. This is a surprising result since for the epoxy nanocomposites modified solely with either CSR particles or silica nanoparticles, a significant

reduction in toughening is observed at high rates of loading. The exact nature of the synergy in these heavily loaded hybrids is not well understood and is the focus of continuing investigation by the authors.

The cone was used to measure the time to ignition and core temperatures at ignition, as well as to analyse the surface charring. An example of a tested sample is given in Figure 1.

The results reveal that the addition of silica nanoparticles increases the time to ignition as well as the core temperatures. This is in agreement with previous measurements by Roenner et al. [2]. They explained that this increase in flammability resistance was due to two separate effects working in parallel: (1) a formation of a char mass barrier leading to the formation of an almost continuous skin. As this skin hinders the flow of flammable pyrolysis gases, less pyrolysate is released into the environment, delaying the formation of a flammable mixture above the sample, and hence ignition; (2) an increase in thermal diffusivity which leads to an increase in core temperature and thermal gradients through the sample, while the surface temperature is reduced, delaying the time to ignition.

4 Conclusion

Simultaneously tough and fire resistant epoxy nanocomposites have been manufactured by heavily loading the epoxy matrix with silica nanoparticles. The toughening effects of rubber particles are found to be far greater than for silica nanoparticles. The potential to create hybrid nanocomposites that are an order of magnitude tougher than existing epoxy resins as well as demonstrating vastly improved fire resistance is outlined. These epoxy nanocomposites can then be used as the matrix in carbon fibre laminates as demonstrated by Carolan et al. [3].

References

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Fig.1. Cone rig set up (left). Top view of 0% nanofiller sample surface after ignitions (right).

Fig.2. Fracture energy of silica nanoparticle modified epoxy composites versus silica content.

Fig.3. Fracture energy of core shell rubber nanoparticle modified epoxy composites versus CSR content.